

The Hamiltonian and Time Evolution for Classical Statistical Systems and Quantum Systems And A Possible Physical Origin of $\exp(iEt)$ in the Wavefunction

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B Sept. 25, 2018

We consider the possibility that both classical statistical mechanical systems as well as quantum mechanical time independent systems evolve according to the Hamiltonian H . This suggests that given the energy of the system, the Hamiltonian operating on a density or wavefunction will bring back the density or wavefunction with a weight factor of E , energy. For the quantum mechanical case, E represents a frequency. We argue that it is a frequency for both the quantum and statistical mechanical case, related to how quickly the system interacts under the Hamiltonian. We also examine an aspect of interference in the quantum wavefunction which may be related to a 2×2 model of a particle which cycles back and forth as it moves with an average velocity v in a certain direction. We argue that the plane waves stirred up in a potential (or in the Fourier series of the wavefunction) are associated with periodic time motion (due to zitterbewegung). We argue that as these plane waves interfere, they create a new constant average energy throughout a system with a potential which acts as the period of periodic time behaviour, namely $\exp(iEt)$

Statistical Mechanics and the Hamiltonian as an Evolution Operator

Classical statistical mechanics for an equilibrium situation is often derived using the Boltzmann transport equation or by maximizing entropy subject to constraints. It is suggested that one can attempt to view an equilibrium situation as one in which the Hamiltonian operating on a statistical distribution returns the distribution with a weight of E . In general, for a system with a potential $V(x)$, one would have a density $d(x,t, E)$ where E is the energy. (We consider one dimension here) with a Hamiltonian $H = KE + V(x) + H_{\text{collision}}$. For statistical mechanics, the collision term is the dominant term, in fact, statistical mechanics for equilibrium situations appears to be based on the idea of collisions creating a constant temperature everywhere even if the potential $V(x)$ is changing from point to point. Alternatively, a particle has an average KE of $.5 RT$ (in 1 dim) anywhere in the system. If this is the case, then density is separable, namely $f(p) d1(x)$, where $f(p)$ is a momentum density due to collisions and $d1(x)$ a spatial density due to $V(x)$. Both of these should be derivable using ideas of evolution under the Hamiltonian. To obtain $f(p)$ one can consider collisions between two particles which conserve kinetic energy and momentum. Then, one can write the Boltzmann result automatically, namely:

$f(p_1)f(p_2)=f(p_3)f(p_4)$ where p_1 and p_2 are the momentum vectors before the collision and p_3 and p_4 after. This follows from probability theory as $f(p_1)$ is the probability to have a particle with p_1 at x and $f(p_2)$ to have a particle p_2 at x . Note, that $f(p_1)$ does not depend on x . Collisions make the distribution $f(p)$ the same everywhere even if there is a potential. One has an "and" situation, namely a particle with p_1 "and" one with "p2" collide. Using conservation of kinetic energy leads to the Boltzmann factor for $f(p)$.

For the spatial part $d1(x)$, one can consider a particle with momentum p at x . This particle will move into a region where the potential will slow it down (as an example). To have equilibrium, one may argue that:

$$d1(x) f(p^2/2m + V) = d1(x+dx) f(p^2/2m + V + dV/dx dx)$$

The equal sign ensures that there is no change in time. Performing a Taylor series, and using the Boltzmann form for $f(p)$ leads to:

$$0 = -dV/dx (1/T) d1(x) - d d1(x)/dx$$

This is the common pressure balance equation which appears in statistical mechanical textbooks.

Thus, the idea of a Hamiltonian as an evolution operator in classical statistical mechanics appears to lead to the usual statistical mechanical density results. An extra idea, however, is that a Hamiltonian acting on a density should return the density together with a factor of E , the average energy. For different average energies this value will be different. It is suggested that for different energies, there is a different cycling time in a statistical system. For example, one may suggest preparing a system with an equilibrium distribution and then allowing the Hamiltonian to act on it and observing the result. In this hypothetical scenario, it is argued that it would take a time $1/E$ for the Hamiltonian to finish interacting in the system. (For a physical system, the Hamiltonian is acting at all times.) Thus, there may possibly be a kind of periodicity in statistical systems.

It should be noted that in classical statistical mechanical systems, the average kinetic energy of a particle at any position x is a constant and not the average kinetic energy plus potential energy. This is a very different constraint than that which appears in quantum mechanics.

The Hamiltonian as an Evolution Operator in Quantum Mechanics.

In quantum mechanics, it seems that one can consider an ensemble of plane wave momentum eigenfunctions (or $\sin(kx)$) with weights making up a Fourier series of what is called a wavefunction (see [2]). The logarithm of the wavefunction appears to behave as a partition function, but carries a position dependent probability. In general, a Fourier series is a mathematical construct, but for the wavefunction it appears to have physical meaning as it contains all of the plane waves which can be stirred up by the potential. (Even for nuclei, a Fourier series of the wavefunction which contains angular eigenfunctions indicates rotation of the nucleus, even in the ground state.) For the quantum mechanical case, the average kinetic energy at x plus $V(x)$ (the potential at x) must add to the total energy E at each point, unlike in classical statistical mechanics (see [2]). In other words:

$$\hbar^2/2m (d/dx)^2 W(x) / W(x) = \text{average kinetic energy} \quad (1)$$

In the case of quantum mechanics, like classical statistical mechanics, operating with the Hamiltonian on the wavefunction is like operating with part of an evolution operator and should yield the wavefunction, the original ensemble, with a factor of E . This factor of E may again be associated with $1/\text{time}$ and may indicate the amount of time for the system to interact to see if the ensemble has evolved or not. Thus, there is an overall periodicity in the problem equal to $\exp(iEt)$.

Aspects of Interference in Quantum Mechanics

In quantum mechanics, it has been argued in [2] that :

$$\sin(px) f(p)/W(x) \quad (\text{a term in the Fourier series of } W(x) \text{ divided by } W(x)) \quad (2)$$

represents a probability associated with momentum p (moving forward and backward). It was further argued that this is a conditional probability, namely $P(p \text{ given } x)$ and that $P(x) = W(x)*W(x)$ (see []). This causes one to question the physical meaning of $\sin(px)$. First of all, $\sin(px)$ is a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, which are "eigenfunctions" of momentum for a particle moving to the left and right. Now, each of these eigenfunctions contains a real part of $\cos(px)$ which can be either positive or negative, depending on x . The question is what does the negative sign mean? In the 2×2 matrix model [4], a particle moving to the right with speed v is modeled in a quantum mechanical way as bouncing to the right and left while moving on average with v in one direction. In such a case, there is a natural cycle or period to this particle, whether it is moving to the left or right overall. The negative part of $\cos(px)$ may represent part of the cycle. For a particle in a well with an infinite potential at $x=0$ and $x=a$, one has a wavefunction $W(x)$ of $\sin(px)$. If one uses (2), the average kinetic energy everywhere is proportional to p^2 , because $\sin(px)$ divides out from the numerator and denominator. The probability density $W(x)*W(x)$, however, can be zero at certain points and the kinetic energy density is also zero at these points. Thus, it is a little strange to have a non-zero average kinetic energy at a point where the probability density and kinetic energy density are zero.

If one has a potential $V(x)$ which stirs up many plane waves, the average kinetic energy (1), at a particular point can have positive contributions ($\sin(px)>0$ at x) from some p values and negative ($\sin(px)<0$ at x) from others (which are on the negative part of their cycles). This is very peculiar as a regular averaging process would note that kinetic energy is always positive and that there are no cycles in the problem. In the quantum mechanical problem, it appears that when taking averages, nature considers the presence of different cycles of different p 's at the same point x as interfering like waves. This has been known since the beginning of quantum mechanics, but the puzzling feature was that it was argued that no physical wave was present. In the 2×2 matrix model [4], it was argued that a particle had complicated zitterbewegung periodic motion associated with its average motion of v in one direction. It is possible that there

is a physical reversal of some properties as the particles moves from the "positive" part of its cycle to the "negative" perhaps justifying the wavelike addition or cancellation of different kinetic energies at a point.

This point has been highlighted because many there are many statistical theories which are used to derive the Schrodinger equation [3] on a purely statistical basis or using stochastic motion, but perhaps do not deal directly with the nature of interference in the quantum mechanical system. It was noted in [2], that perhaps systems with wavemotion (e.g. containing sound waves) in classical physics could exhibit quantum mechanical like statistics in certain cases.)

The idea of interference is not just limited to the "plane waves" stirred up by the potential. In a two slit experiment, it has been argued in [5] that zitterbewegung causes the particle to undergo complicated motion within a region about its average motion. It is argued that there may be nonlocal collisions occurring within this region which is the size of a wavelength. As a result, a particle moving with an average velocity of v would be able to change direction in a very strange way. Imagine that the average motion of a particle is taking it through one slit of a two slit system. Due to zitterbewegung, it might interact with the second slit. Such an interaction should, however, "stir up" a different plane wave (like in the bound Schrodinger equation case described above). This second plane wave should then interfere with the first in the same manner as described for the quantum bound state. Again, a strange averaging is occurring with opposite cycles cancelling.

Zitterbewegung and $\exp(iEt)$ for a System with a Potential

In the 2x2 matrix model [4], Einstein's 1905 energy momentum equation $p^2 + m^2 = E^2$ was written as a linear matrix equation similar to the Dirac equation. From this, it was found that a particle moves with an average v while undergoing periodic zitterbewegung motion. It was suggested in [1] that such a particle could be modeled by $\exp(ikx)$ in spatial equilibrium setting, where the time periodicity of $\exp(iEt)$ is related to the spatial periodicity of $\exp(ikx)$. Then, one could imagine a system with a potential stirring up many different plane wave $\exp(ikx)$ which could interfere to create a system with an average kinetic energy at each point such that this average kinetic energy plus potential energy equaled a fixed energy E . This interference has been discussed above. A question arises as to whether this new system with a fixed E everywhere has any time periodicity (like the 2x2 particle) and if so, what the frequency would be.

It was noted in [1] that one could consider decomposing $V(x)$ in a Fourier series and applying this to the time independent Schrodinger equation with the wavefunction $W(x)$ also written in its Fourier decomposition. Then for any p one has:

$$\hbar^2/2m p^2 a_p \exp(ipx) + \sum V_i \exp(i k_i x) a_{kj} \exp i(k_j x) \text{ (where } k_i+k_j=p) = E a_p \exp(ipx) \quad (3)$$

Here a_p is the weight of $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus, different k_j values from different stirred up plane waves are combining with the potential to create waves matching the $\exp(ipx)$ wave. The overall coefficient is leading to E . It should be noted, however, that one can write (3) for every p . Thus, a plane wave k_j is part of the combination (3) for one p , but then is part of a different combination for another p . Thus, it seems that the system may be jumping from one combination (3) to another.

It should be noted that it was argued in [1] that the $\exp(ikx)$ spatial plane wave was part of the relativistically invariant expression $\exp(iEt-kx)$. Thus, even though $\exp(ikx)$ is being used in the equilibrium time independent Schrodinger case, there is an associated periodic time piece. Thus, the term $\sin(kx)$ (from a forward and backward plane wave) does not just represent a spatial distribution, but also time periodicity. Now (3), which holds for all p (momentum) values would be written as: $\hbar^2/2m p^2 \exp(ipx) = E \exp(ipx)$ if there were not potential. Then there would be zitterbewegung of $\exp(iEt)$ in the problem. The equation is generalized with each $\sin(px)$ leading to a right hand side of $E \sin(px)$ and so it seems that one might infer that E is the time periodicity in this case for all $\sin(px)$ in the time independent Schrodinger equilibrium scenario. The point seems to be that even though (3) is an equation with no explicit time variable present, time is implied because $\sin(px)$ (from forward and backward motion) is automatically associated with time periodicity. The different plane waves have interfered to create a spatial distribution leading to conservation of energy everywhere, but also seem to have created a new time periodicity equal to the new total energy E . This is important as it suggests that components with zitterbewegung can interfere and combine to form larger systems with new total energies which are associated with periodic time motion.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have argued that both classical and quantum mechanical bound systems come into equilibrium when the Hamiltonian acting on the system does not change the statistical distribution. For the case of classical statistical mechanics, the distribution is $\exp(-[KE+V]/T)$ where KE is the kinetic energy and V , the potential. For quantum mechanics, things are more complicated because the plane waves stirred up by the potential represent 2×2 matrix model particle states which have zitterbewegung. These different states can interfere in an interesting way to ensure constant energy ($KE+V$) at each point. We argue that even though one can write a Fourier transform of the wavefunction to describe these 2×2 matrix particle states, they automatically contain periodic time information. If the system is able to come into an equilibrium situation such that $(\hbar^2 p^2/2m + V) \sin(px) = E \sin(px)$ for each p , it is as if one has each plane wave with a periodic time dependence of $\exp(iEt)$ where E is the constant energy in the system. If there were not potential, there would be one p and $E = \hbar^2 p^2/2m$.

References

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